

Knowledge, Attitude and Behavior of Jumantik in Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever

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Abstract

Introduction: Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) is an endemic disease that occurs throughout the year during the rainy season, the optimal condition for the reproduction of *Aedes aegypti* mosquitos. The most effective effort to prevent DHF is through the eradication of mosquito nests (PSN) with the One House One Jumantik Program (G1R1J), focused on the role of household members to carry out periodic larva monitoring (PJB), as well as through 3M Plus activities. Knowledge, attitude and behavior are interrelated.

Purpose: This study aims to describe the knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of Family Jumantik regarding the prevention of DHF. **Methods:** This research is a quantitative descriptive study with a cross sectional time approach, with the research instrument in the form of a questionnaire. The sampling technique uses the method accidental sampling with the research subject, namely Family Jumantik in South Denpasar District which meets the criteria. The research data were analyzed by descriptive statistical method using a SPSS program. **Results:** The results of this study show that from 110 Jumantik, the majority are aged 20-60 years, with male sex. The last education of Jumantik was in college, with the majority of work as students. The results showed that Family Jumantik had a level of knowledge (65.5%), attitudes (57.3%), and behavior (70.0%) about DHF prevention.

Conclusion: There is a positive trend between the knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of the community regarding the prevention of DHF.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Behavior, Prevention of DHF

INTRODUCTION

Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) is an endemic disease that occurs year-round, especially during the rainy season, which provides optimal conditions for the breeding of the vectors that cause DHF.⁽¹⁾ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Indonesia ranks first in Southeast Asia for the highest number of DHF cases. Since 1968 to 2009, the number of DHF cases and the geographical spread of the disease have increased, in line with population density and mobility growth.⁽²⁾

To assess DHF control efforts in Indonesia, the indicator used is the Larvae-Free Index (LFI). The national

target for LFI is set at >95.0%. In the last two years, the LFI has not met the national target, although there was an increase from the previous year's 31.5% (2018) to 79.2% (2019).⁽³⁾ The national target for the Incidence Rate (IR) of DHF is <49 per 100,000 population. In 2019, 23 provinces had not yet met the IR target of <49 per 100,000 population, including Bali Province with an IR of 114.8 per 100,000 population.⁽³⁾ Denpasar City is the capital of Bali Province, with high population density and mobility, which contributes to the high number of DHF cases. DHF cases in Denpasar City fluctuated over the past five years, with 2,851 cases (2016), 928 cases (2017), 113 cases (2018),⁽⁴⁾ 1,220

cases (2019),⁽⁵⁾ and 1,501 cases (2020).⁽⁶⁾ South Denpasar District is one of the four districts in Denpasar City that contributed the highest number of DHF cases.⁽⁷⁾ In 2020, South Denpasar District ranked first in DHF cases.⁽⁶⁾ The number of DHF cases in South Denpasar District over the past five years was 1,074 cases (2016), 290 cases (2017), 33 cases (2018),⁽⁷⁾ 391 cases (January-July 2019),⁽⁸⁾ and 612 cases (2020) with an IR of 196.41 per 100,000 population.⁽⁶⁾ The IR for DHF cases in 2020 in South Denpasar District did not meet the national target of <49 per 100,000 population.

In the implementation of the Healthy Indonesia Program 2016 with a Family Approach, the Ministry of Health launched the One House, One Larvae Monitor Movement, conducted nationally, emphasizing the role of household members in conducting larvae monitoring (PJB) and mosquito nest eradication (PSN) through 3M Plus activities.⁽⁹⁾ This is considered the most effective effort to eradicate mosquito breeding sites. The Denpasar City government's policy to meet the national DHF IR target is to carry out PSN⁽¹⁰⁾ activities and regularly monitor larvae in homes through Larvae Monitoring Officers (Jumantik), along with a community movement involving one house, one Jumantik.⁽¹¹⁾ A 2020 study in South Denpasar District revealed that

most Jumantik volunteers in the district actively participated.⁽⁷⁾

Knowledge, attitudes, and behavior are three interrelated factors. If only one aspect is good while the others are lacking, the outcome may be insignificant.⁽¹²⁾ Knowledge, as a form of DHF prevention behavior in the community, can be evaluated in simpler environments like families.⁽¹³⁾ Based on the above explanation, the researcher is interested in exploring the knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of Family Jumantik in preventing DHF in South Denpasar District.

METHODS

This study is a quantitative descriptive research with a cross-sectional time approach conducted in Denpasar Selatan District from January to February 2022. The sampling technique used is accidental sampling, with research subjects being family Jumantik in Denpasar Selatan District who meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The variables to be studied include knowledge, attitudes, and behavior regarding the prevention of dengue fever (DBD). Data analysis is performed using descriptive statistical methods with SPSS software.

RESULTS

Table 1. Characteristics of Family Mosquito Larvae

Characteristics	Frecuency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-30 years old	79	71.8
31-40 years old	7	6.3
41-50 years old	10	8.2
51- 60 years old	14	12.7
Total	110	100.0
Gender		
Men	60	54.5
Women	50	45.5
Total	110	100.0
Education		
Collage	101	91.8

Senior High School	5	4.5
Elementary School, Junior High School	4	3.6
Total	110	100.0
Occupation		
Student	44	40.0
Self-Employed	33	30.0
Employee	11	10.0
Housewife	9	8.2
Not working	13	11.8
Total	110	100.0

Table 1 shows that family Jumantik are in their productive age, with the majority in the 20-30 year age range, totaling 79 people (71.8%). The majority are male, numbering 60 people (54.5%). In terms of educational background, most family Jumantik have higher education, totaling 101 people (91.8%), and most of them are students, totaling 44 people (40.0%).

Table 2 shows the distribution of knowledge among family Jumantik based on a questionnaire, with the majority having good knowledge, above 70.0%, about aspects such as understanding, causes, modes of transmission, sources of dengue fever (DBD), and activities related to 3M Plus. There are two statements with results below 70.0%, specifically on the question about the flying range of *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes (59.0%) and symptoms of DBD (53.0%).

Table 3 shows the distribution of attitudes among family Jumantik based on a questionnaire, with the majority

agreeing on statements above 70.0%. However, there is one statement with a result below 70.0%, specifically question number 10 about cleaning tree fronds to prevent *Aedes aegypti* mosquito breeding (67.0%).

Table 4 shows the results of the observation of the behavior of family Jumantik regarding DBD prevention activities, with the majority displaying good behavior above 70.0%. However, there are some incorrect behaviors, such as not using mesh on home ventilation (56.0%), not using mosquito nets (74%), and hanging clothes indiscriminately (80.0%).

Table 5 shows the distribution of the levels of knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of family Jumantik about DBD prevention. The majority have good knowledge, with 72 people (65.5%), good attitudes, with 62 people (57.3%), and good behavior, with 77 people (70.0%) regarding DBD prevention.

Table 2. Results of The Family Jumantik Knowledge Level Questionnaire

No.	Question	Correct (%)	Wrong (%)
1.	What is Dengue Fever (DBD)?	78 (71.0)	32 (29.0)
2.	What causes Dengue Fever (DBD)?	91 (83.0)	19 (17.0)
3.	What are the symptoms of Dengue Fever (DBD)?	52 (47.0)	58 (53.0)
4.	Name one clinical symptom of Dengue Fever (DBD)?	80 (73.0)	30 (27.0)
5.	What transmits Dengue Fever (DBD)?	108(98.0)	2 (2.0)
6.	How far can <i>Aedes aegypti</i> mosquitoes fly?	45 (41.0)	65 (59.0)
7.	Who can contract Dengue Fever (DBD)?	86 (78.0)	24 (22.0)

8.	When do Aedes aegypti mosquitoes typically bite humans?	67 (61.0)	43 (39.0)
9.	Name one breeding site of the mosquito that transmits Dengue Fever (DBD)?	86 (78.0)	24 (22.0)
10.	What does PSN stand for?	107 (97.0)	3 (3.0)
11.	What is the name of the method to prevent Dengue Fever (DBD)?	109 (99.0)	1 (1.0)
12.	Name the three main activities in Dengue Fever (DBD) prevention.	80 (73.0)	30 (27.0)
13.	Give an example of Dengue Fever (DBD) prevention in daily life.	89 (81.0)	21 (19.0)
14.	How often should water tanks be drained at a minimum per week?	110 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
15.	One way to kill Aedes aegypti mosquito larvae is by sprinkling what?	102 (93.0)	8 (7.0)

Table 3. Results of the Family Jumantik Attitude Level Questionnaire

No.	Question	Agree (%)	Don't Agree (%)
1.	Drain the bathtub at least once a week as one of the measures to prevent Dengue Fever (DBD).	77 (70.0)	33 (30.0)
2.	Aedes aegypti mosquito eggs can stick to the walls and bottom of the bathtub, so they must be brushed off when draining.	82 (75.0)	28 (25.0)
3.	Cover water storage containers as a preventive measure to stop Aedes aegypti mosquitoes from laying eggs.	84 (76.0)	26 (24.0)
4.	Bury used cans to prevent the breeding of Aedes aegypti mosquitoes.	78 (71.0)	32 (29.0)
5.	Keep fish in water storage containers that can eat Aedes aegypti mosquito larvae.	77 (70.0)	33 (30.0)
6.	Replace water in flower vases and bird drinking containers at least once a week to prevent the breeding of Aedes aegypti mosquitoes.	77 (70.0)	33 (30.0)
7.	Water storage containers that are difficult to drain should be treated with larvicides like Abate powder.	82 (75.0)	28 (25.0)
8.	Clean clogged or slow-draining water channels immediately.	82 (75.0)	28 (25.0)
9.	Use water storage containers that are easy to clean so that they can be drained and scrubbed easily.	80 (73.0)	30 (27.0)
10.	Clean tree fronds to prevent the breeding of Aedes aegypti mosquitoes.	74 (67.0)	36 (33.0)

Table 4. Results of the Family Jumantik Behavior Level Questionnaire

No.	Observation	Good (%)	Poor (%)
1.	House condition?	101 (92.0)	9 (8.0)
2.	Habit of draining the bathtub?	63 (57.0)	47 (43.0)
3.	Condition of the water in water storage containers?	102 (93.0)	8 (7.0)
4.	Water storage containers?	80 (73.0)	30 (27.0)
5.	How are used items/cans that can collect water disposed of?	88 (80.0)	22 (20.0)

6.	Condition of clothes hanging?	30 (27.0)	80 (73.0)
7.	Use of mesh on home ventilation?	48 (44.0)	62 (56.0)
8.	Lighting inside the house?	90 (82.0)	20 (18.0)
9.	Presence of mosquito larvae?	85 (77.0)	25 (23.0)
10.	Use of mosquito nets?	29 (26.0)	81 (74.0)

Table 5. Distribution of Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Behavior of Family Jumantik about Dengue Fever Prevention

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Knowledge		
Good	72	65.5
Enough	18	16.4
Poor	20	18.2
Total	110	100.0
Attitude		
Good	63	57.3
Enough	23	20.9
Poor	24	21.8
Total	110	100.0
Behavior		
Good	77	70.0
Poor	33	30.0
Total	110	100.0

DISCUSSION

The educational characteristics of family Jumantik in this study show that the majority have a higher education level (91.8%), with most being students (40.0%). Education level affects a person's ability to filter the information they receive, which can influence their ability to pay attention to both their own and their family's health.⁽¹⁴⁾ This study shows that the majority of family Jumantik have good knowledge about DBD prevention (65.5%). However, there are still misunderstandings among family Jumantik regarding the DBD vector (59.0%) and symptoms of DBD (53.0%).

This could potentially affect their attitudes and actions. According to Notoatmodjo, knowledge about the causes, symptoms, vectors, methods, places of transmission, objectives and benefits, as well as the negative impacts of not performing DBD prevention with 3M Plus, can motivate someone to adopt and enhance behavior in DBD prevention with

3M Plus. Efforts to improve public awareness and perception on this matter include increasing the frequency of DBD prevention outreach.⁽¹⁵⁾

According to the Health Belief Model theory, which predicts and explains individual behavior, attitudes and perceptions are important factors. A person's attitude or perspective influences their actions; therefore, a more positive attitude or perspective leads to better actions. A similar study by Wardoyo, Putri, and Duarsa (2021) found that the majority of respondents had moderate attitudes (73.1%). This was attributed to the availability of facilities. Factors such as infrastructure can affect one's attitude, and good knowledge alone does not guarantee a positive attitude.⁽¹²⁾⁽¹⁵⁾ This study shows that the majority of family Jumantik have a good attitude (57.3%). However, there is a misconception among family Jumantik, as most do not agree with cleaning tree fronds to prevent *Aedes aegypti* mosquito breeding (67.0%).

Family Jumantik's awareness of maintaining cleanliness in their homes and surroundings is still lacking, which does not align with the essence of 3M Plus, which involves cleaning all places at risk of *Aedes aegypti* mosquito breeding.⁽¹²⁾⁽¹⁶⁾ Those who do not agree with DBD prevention efforts tend to be less concerned about environmental cleanliness.⁽¹²⁾⁽¹⁴⁾

Family Jumantik's behavior regarding DBD prevention shows that most exhibit good behavior (70.0%). This might be due to current government regulations during the COVID-19 pandemic, which involved several protective and control measures to reduce the spread of the virus, such as lockdowns, travel bans, school closures, class postponements, and transitioning to online learning and working from home.⁽¹⁷⁾⁽¹⁸⁾ The researcher assumes this is related to the availability of time for family Jumantik to engage in DBD prevention. Research by Triyani (2021) in Mertan village, Sukaharjo, supports this by stating that the COVID-19 pandemic led Mertan village respondents to maintain better home cleanliness, such as draining water tanks, etc.⁽¹⁹⁾ However, observations reveal that family Jumantik still has problematic habits, such as hanging clothes indiscriminately (73.0%), not using mesh on home ventilation (56.0%), and not using mosquito nets (74.0%).

The findings indicate that family Jumantik in Denpasar Selatan District have good knowledge, attitudes, and behavior regarding DBD prevention, but there are still some misconceptions. This suggests that evaluation and increased intensity in DBD prevention outreach need to be further improved.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Family Jumantik in Denpasar Selatan District with good knowledge about DBD prevention amounts to 72 people (65.5%).
2. Family Jumantik in Denpasar Selatan District with a good attitude toward DBD prevention amounts to 63 people (57.3%).
3. Family Jumantik in Denpasar Selatan District with good behavior regarding DBD prevention amounts to 77 people (70.0%).

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